

The InnoWEE Project: from waste to energy efficiency

Il progetto InnoWEE: dai materiali di scarto all'efficienza energetica

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ABSTRACT: InnoWEE Project “Innovative pre-fabricated components including different waste construction materials reducing building energy and minimizing environmental impacts” is a four year project (from 2016 to 2020) financed by the European Commission as part of H2020 program involving ten partners from different European countries, Greece, Italy, Romania, Slovenia, Spain and Poland. The aim of the project is to use the waste materials coming from construction and demolition processes of buildings and then include them into a geopolymeric matrix with the purpose of producing prefabricated panels for different applications. Construction and demolition waste (CDW) materials with suitable characteristics are selected to develop high performance geopolymeric panels for building walls envelopes and radiating panels for indoor walls and ceilings with low environmental impact. Installation tests will be carried out in different real sites in Europe under different climatic conditions to check the simplicity of the installation and the performances of the panels in terms of energy reduction and environmental impacts. / Il progetto InnoWEE “Innovative pre-fabricated components including different waste construction materials reducing building energy and minimizing environmental impacts” è un progetto con durata prevista di quattro anni (dal 2016 al 2020) finanziato dalla Commissione Europea nell'ambito del programma H2020 che coinvolge dieci partner provenienti da diversi paesi europei, Grecia, Italia, Romania, Slovenia, Spagna e Polonia. Lo scopo del progetto è quello di utilizzare materiali di scarto provenienti dal processo di costruzione e demolizione degli edifici per sviluppare pannelli geopolimerici prestazionali per diverse applicazioni. I pannelli geopolimerici standard verranno utilizzati per il tamponamento esterno degli edifici mentre i pannelli geopolimerici radianti serviranno a rivestire internamente pareti e soffitti. Il progetto prevede inoltre test di installazione per valutare la facilità di montaggio e le prestazioni dei pannelli in termini di riduzione del consumo energetico e dell'impatto ambientale.

KEYWORDS: geopolymers; construction and demolition waste materials; installation methods; energy efficient building / geopolimeri; materiali di scarto da costruzioni e demolizioni; metodi di installazione; efficienza energetica degli edifici

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Construction Sector

In Europe, the construction sector is one of the major consumers of natural resources, so it is necessary to focus on the building industry to limit consumption and waste of energy. When referring to “construction sector” all phases, starting from the supply of the material up to the disposal and recovery activities, should be considered. A more appropriate use of materials should ensure a greater contribution to reducing the environmental impact.

It is therefore interesting to consider the potential reuse of CDW materials, possibly by looking for innovative solutions that also reduce building energy consumption.

The selective dismantling of building components is becoming increasingly urgent. It is needed to reuse the individual components following a Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) approach including a Life Cycle

Analysis (LCA) to support environmental decisions complementing the waste hierarchy. The construction sector is already heavily involved in waste recovery, particularly in concrete, metal and plastic, but also in glass and wood.

Current technologies though are not efficient enough in terms of performances and costs and especially in terms of satisfactory and innovative solutions. The main objective of InnoWEE is therefore the development of new solutions that are economically viable, by developing flexible and modular panels, made by processing high amounts of CDW while reaching at the same time a high performance in terms of energy efficiency and environmental impact.

1.2 The Project's objectives

InnoWEE [1] is a research project that aims to identify new technological solutions able to make more profitable use of the waste materials deriving from demolished buildings to reduce wastefulness of the building sector.

The challenge is to develop real and efficient solutions, both in terms of performances and costs, developing innovative products deriving from existing building waste materials, thus creating new opportunities in business and real estate development. The idea is to produce high performance prefabricated geopolymer panels to be used for different applications: as an external wall system (ETICS and ventilated façades) or as indoor ecofriendly radiating panels (for wall and ceiling installations).

The panels produced will be first installed in a “pilot site” to check the ease of installation and later will be installed in three real “demo sites” in order to monitor their energy performances. The research also focuses on energy simulations carried out on “virtual sites” characterized by different climatic conditions in order to have a complete picture of the insulating behavior of the panels. The installed panel will be monitored to check both energy savings and environmental sustainability.

An important issue is to evaluate the possibility of successful market entry of the new materials and solutions, taking into account the competitiveness of the products, considering not only the performances but also the economical aspects. In addition, guidelines will be developed to find out how to install panels and provide explanations regarding the new solutions studied, in order to disseminate the results.

Therefore, the InnoWEE project could be the starting point for the development of further innovative technologies.

2 PILLARS

The InnoWEE Project is trying to satisfy several important topics for our society: infact, many aspects are taken into account, starting from environmental and technological issues, to economical ones (Fig. 1) [2].

2.1 Economic and marketing pillar

The development of the project is based on gathering information about the current materials and solutions known in the field of prefabricated constructions. Starting from this information a preliminary business plan is designed to explore both the opportunities and barriers in the market, considering aspects of different nature such as: costs of materials, production effectiveness, external impacts, process phases of installation, maintenance and more.

Competitive and reliable solutions for the market are developed with products easy to integrate into building designs and easy to install.

2.2 Scientific pillar

The scientific part of the project consists in the development of a suitable geopolymer binder able to include high amounts of CDW (40- 60% by weight of concrete, fired clay brick waste and/or wood waste) and use the binder to produce prototypes of innovative geopolymer panels that improve outdoor and indoor behavior of walls and ceilings. Starting from the recovery, selection and disassembly of CDW, innovative high performance prefabricated geopolymer panels for insulating façades as well as more eco-friendly radiating panel systems for wall and ceiling are developed and tested under different climate conditions and architectonic requirements [3].

2.3 Enviromental and Energy pillar

All the studies are based on an LCA approach and the evaluation of the embodied energy saving at the building level and inside the whole life cycle will be performed. The modeling of the performance in terms of Energy efficiency and environmental sustainability will be carried out in real and “virtual” case studies.

The project aims to demonstrate that the products and the solutions will strengthen the competitiveness of the European construction sector in the field of “green” construction technologies being the new solutions composed mainly by “green” materials.

Figure 1. Diagram of the main pillars of InnoWEE project / Schema riguardante i capisaldi del progetto InnoWEE.

3 GEOPOLYMER PANELS

The development of the project is based on a circular process supported by the information about the current materials and solutions available in the prefabricated construction field (Fig. 2). Here begins the op-

timization and the production of the new products to install and to monitor. The identification of waste materials and subsequent production of the geopolymer panels is one of the main steps as well as the starting point of the InnoWEE project [4].

Figure 2. Diagram explaining the circular process of the project / Diagramma esplicativo del processo ciclico del progetto.

3.1 Recycling process of CDW

There is a high potential for recycling and re-use of CDW, since some of its components have a high value. Whenever possible the first option is direct re-use of waste materials instead of recycling. Unfortunately, this option is rarely possible.

The recycling process of CDW involves basically three phases.

First of all, the production and collection of the waste: a selective demolition process is used. It consists in dismantling the building to separate different streams of waste materials to facilitate re-use and recycling. This kind of demolition requires a reorganization of the demolition site, mostly for smaller sites (92% of the waste in Italy).

The second phase consists in the treatment of the waste in special plants, according to local regulations. The recycling process will thus yield new materials, called secondary raw materials (SRM) [5]. Each material has a different recycling process. Recycled materials can be recovered from concrete, glass, wood, bricks, plastics and metals.

The last phase is to reintroduce the secondary raw materials into the market.

3.2 Characterization of CDW materials

The first step involves the characterization of the waste materials. On the base of a LCA approach the definition and selection of the CDW is the first phase that has been taken into account to create in-

novative solutions that improve the environment and saving energy during the whole life cycle.

The identification of the typologies of CDW useful to be mixed with the geopolymer matrix to build the prefabricated panels was carried out. The CDW were selected based on their properties, analyzed in research laboratories and then the production lines of the recycling company involved in the project have been adapted. Then the CDW materials were mixed with a geopolymer matrix optimized to successfully produce the innovative panels.

In parallel with the research work on CDW materials to be used, the framework for the panels production has been designed, taking into account the standards and guidelines to be respected as well as the costs of the competitive alternatives.

3.3 Geopolymers

Geopolymers are inorganic polymers obtained from the reaction of an aluminosilicate powder with an aqueous alkaline solution. They belong to the broader class of chemically activated ceramics. Depending on the raw material selection, aggregates and filler used and processing conditions, geopolymers can exhibit a wide variety of properties and characteristics including high compressive strength, low shrinkage, short setting time, good resistance to chemicals. Geopolymers are green materials for a sustainable economy since they easily allow recycling a large range of industrial wastes thereby reducing the consumption of natural resources.

Geopolymers present also an interesting alternative to recycle inorganic CDW in the case of prefabricated component production where conditions can be well controlled, since they yield products that will have a lower CO₂ emission contribution than new concrete made from recycled aggregates. In addition, geopolymers appear to be more suitable to recycle a greater variety of CDW than concrete, including also organic CDW such as wood. Indeed, geopolymers are an inorganic binder that can be used similarly to historically used magnesite or Portland cement binders for producing cement bonded wood-wool panels and cement bonded particle boards.

4 PRODUCTION OF PANELS

After selecting and researching materials useful to create geopolymer panels, the second step was to think about a production system to create the innovative panels, including: two new eco-friendly insulating façade panels incorporating min 40-60% of selected CDW and two types of eco-friendly radiating panels for indoor wall and ceiling installations respectively.

During the first stage an optimized geopolymer binder including the CDW was developed. Then the

work on the previously selected waste combined with the geopolymer binder and prototype panel fabrication was carried out in the laboratory.

5 INSULATING FAÇADE PANELS

The building envelope is the main heat exchanger element between the building and the external environment, and it is easily responsible for more than 60% of energy losses in a conventional building considering the facades, roofs and windows.

Several systems can be used in buildings to increase the insulating performance of the envelope. However, external thermal insulation composite system (ETICS) and ventilated façade are mostly used.

5.1 ETICS facades: state of the art

This kind of system is known in two different embodiments. The first is a conventional system assembled on-site, while the second one consists in a prefabricated ETICS panel system. In relation to the first system, it foresees application of adhesive, insulation material, mechanical fastenings, base coating, reinforcement nets and finishing coat. On the other hand, the second system is composed by prefabricated panels with a similar structure of conventional system, eventually supported on lightweight steel frames or by conventional ETICS fasteners and adhesives that allow easy fixing to walls.

5.2 ETICS facades: state of design

A new type of ETICS was proposed. It consists of prefabricated insulating panels composed of an outer High Density Geopolymer layer (HDG) and an inner EPS [6] layer (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. New ETICS system / Nuovo sistema di cappotto

To reduce thermal bridges and to make the installation of the panels easier the EPS layers is produced as a double layer (6+2 cm) with the two EPS layers laterally shifted by 7 cm. The final dimension of the panel foreseen will be 40 x 90 cm (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. ETICS prototype test panel / Pannello prototipo di isolamento a cappotto

5.3 Ventilated facades: state of the art

This system consists in an insulating layer fastened to the wall and a facade panel installed on a support frame structure, separating the facade from the insulating layer.

In this way, the resulting air gap allows air circulation, thereby avoiding water vapor condensation on walls and insulating materials.

5.4 Ventilated facades: state of design

Based on the geopolymer technology an innovative ventilated façade panel was designed. The panels are made by bonding an outer HDG layer to an inner wood-geopolymer panel (WGP), thus providing for lightness weight and mechanical strength (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. New ventilated panel / Nuovo pannello per facciata ventilata.

The ventilated façade prototype panels were produced taking into consideration also the methods of fastening to the substructure fixed on the wall. The dimension of the panel is 60 x 60 cm (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Ventilated facade prototype panel / Pannello prototipo per facciata ventilata.

6 RADIATING PANELS

Radiant systems are designed for low temperature heating and high temperature cooling, which can be used in several applications. The radiating panels can be installed on indoor walls or ceilings. The main advantage of these systems is their good energy efficiency.

6.1 Radiating panels: state of the art

Two solutions were studied at this stage. The first is a monolithic panel fabricated by coupling a high density geopolymer layer produced by a casting process to an insulating EPS layer with embedded piping (Fig. 7). The second solution consists in a modular panel that allows more easy disassembly and greater flexibility in the choice of the insulator. In this case the piping is surrounded by a HDG outer layer which is in turn embedded in a WGP inner layer, that is reversibly coupled to an EPS layer (Fig. 8).

Figure 7. First solution of radiant panel / Prima tipologia di pannello radiante.

Figure 8. Second solution of radiant panel / Seconda tipologia di pannello radiante.

6.2 Radiating panels: state of design

An important part of the panels development considered the critical issue of the pipes connection. Two solutions were developed: one related to the ceiling radiant panels which will be connected on the panel backside (Fig. 9), the other to the wall radiant panels that will be connected on the panel side, thus allowing for a reduced installation thickness (Fig. 10).

Figure 9. Radiant ceiling panel (frontside, backside views)/ Pannello radiante a soffitto (vista dei due lati).

Figure 10. Radiant wall panel/ Pannello radiante a parete.

7 INSTALLATION TEST

Before installing the panels on the pilot site, ETIC panels and ventilated panels were installed to a free-standing reinforced concrete wall located in Padua, in Italy, in order to find out potential problems during the installation process (Fig. 11).

The detected problems that arose during the ETIC panels installation were: the difficulty to have a planar façade surface because of the non-planar surface of the support, the problem to adjust in site the verticality of the façade and the too large dimensional tolerances of the produced prototype panels.

During the installation of the ventilated panels the most important problem found referred to the accuracy of the holes on the panels that were drilled on-site by hand [7].

Figure 11. ETIC and ventilated façades in Padua, Italy / Facciata a cappotto e parete ventilata in Padova, Italia.

8 INSTALLATION SITES

The project will foresee to install the panels produced in different sites, starting from a test site, going to real sites and “virtual” ones.

8.1 Pilot site

The pilot site (Pilot House at CNR-Italy, Padua) will be needed to test the innovative materials and solutions in a totally controlled situation, in order to identify possible problems during the future installation phase before to get into the market. In this way, all the detected problems can be studied and solved by industrial partners. The result will be useful to give instructions in the scale up of the products.

The Pilot House (Fig. 12) was built around 1993 as a single-story office building and the structure is made of prefabricated walls. It was used as an office until 2016. In the pilot site all kind of panels will be installed (ETIC, ventilated façade and radiating).

Figure 12. Pilot House at CNR-Italy (Padua) / Pilot House al CNR-Italia (Padova).

Figure 14. Residential eco-house in Belgium (Putte-Mechelen) / Casa ecosostenibile in Belgio (Putte-Mechelen).

8.2 Real demo sites

The panels will be installed also in other three existing buildings, located in different cities of Europe, characterized by different climate conditions.

- Old city hall of Voula municipal, Athens, Greece

This is an historical building, a typical post-modern architecture building. In this site both ETICS and ventilated façade panels will be installed (Fig. 13).

Figure 13. Old city hall of Voula municipal in Greece (Athens) / Antico municipio di Voula in Grecia (Atene).

- Residential eco-house, Putte - Mechelen, Belgium

This is a new residential eco-house, a nZEB (Nearly Zero Energy Building) building. The structure is made of wood. In this site only radiant wall panels will be installed (Fig. 14).

- Don Orione residential care center, Voluntari (Bucharest), Romania

This building is a residential care home for elderly people and orphans with physical and learning disabilities. The charitable structure was established in 2006 as an extension of the well-known Congregation of Don Orione Fathers. In this site only ETICS panels will be installed (Fig. 15).

Figure 15. Don Orione residential care centre in Romania (Bucharest) / Centro residenziale di assistenza Don Orione in Romania (Bucharest).

8.3 "Virtual" sites

Even some "virtual" sites will be considered. Some energetic simulations will be carried out in order to show other examples of panels application.

- Private house, Piazzola sul Brenta (Padua), Italy

This is an apartment inside the Virgins' Cloister of the XVII century.

- Historic building, Parikia (Paros), Greece

This house was built in the beginning of 20th century and is located in the traditional settlement of Parikia in Paros.

- Historical residential building, Bucharest (Romania)

The building is included in the Romanian National Register of Historical Monuments. It was built around 1920 for commercial purposes. Initially the building blended a combination of commercial and residential uses.

- Two blocks in Txurdinaga neighborhood, Bilbao (Spain)

It is formed by two square shape blocks with an inner quad from where the entrance to the houses is done.

9 MONITORING CAMPAIGN

Before and after the installation of the panels in the pilot and real sites, monitoring campaigns will be performed to evaluate the efficiency of the new systems.

The monitoring process will be also useful to check the durability of the panels and by comparison between before and after installation, the thermal properties of the façades.

10 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper first results from the InnoWEE project are presented. InnoWEE focuses on the study and test in field of new high performance prefabricated geopolymer panels made with large content of recycled CDW for building outdoor and indoor walls. This concept was declined in four technological panels, two of them dedicated to the building façade insulation and two to indoor radiative heating/cooling. The products have been developed with different characteristics and a high thermal performance.

After a thorough study of the recycling process of waste material derived from construction and demolition processes, prototypes of three kinds of panels were developed. The demo-sites chosen for installation of upscaled panels have been presented. The buildings chosen as installation sites are completely different among them and are located in places characterized by different climatic conditions.

The different and combined solutions will be assessed in terms of: energy efficiency and environmental sustainability, cost-effectiveness in manufacturing and installation, market potential and exploitability.

Monitoring campaigns will be carried out in order to validate the panels performances and virtual applications will be modeled in different building to check the extension of applicability to different building types and climate.

The evaluation of InnoWEE project will be performed focusing on the following aspects: the energy efficiency, the competitiveness of the panels (according to manufacturing costs and installation), the comfort indoor respect, the applicability also to historical buildings, and eventually the environmental sustainability and reduction of CO₂ production in the atmosphere. / In questo articolo vengono presentati i primi risultati del progetto InnoWEE. Il progetto si è focalizzato sullo studio e sulla verifica in sito di nuovi pannelli geopolimerici prefabbricati ad alte prestazioni, composti in gran parte da materiale di scarto riciclato derivante dal settore delle costruzioni. Questa idea si è tradotta con la produzione di quattro differenti pannelli tecnologici, due di questi per l'isolamento delle facciate esterne degli edifici, le altre due per realizzare sistemi di pannelli radianti di riscaldamento e raffrescamento sia a parete che a soffitto. I prodotti sono stati sviluppati con differenti caratteristiche ed elevate proprietà in termini di trasmittanza termica in relazione al tipo di applicazione.

Dopo un approfondito studio riguardante il riciclo dei materiali di scarto derivanti dalla demolizione nell'ambito delle costruzioni, sono stati prodotti tre tipi di pannelli col fine di installarli in luoghi reali. Gli edifici selezionati per l'installazione sono differenti l'uno dall'altro e i luoghi in cui si collocano sono caratterizzati da diverse condizioni climatiche.

Le diverse soluzioni sono state valutate in termini di efficienza energetica, di sostenibilità ambientale, di efficienza economica per la produzione ed installazione, di potenziale di mercato e di effettivo utilizzo.

Verranno effettuate campagne di monitoraggio a seguito dell'installazione dei pannelli in modo tale da dimostrare la qualità prestazionale dei pannelli. Anche la modellazione di ulteriori applicazioni daranno modo di verificare la loro performance in diversi tipi di edifici e di condizioni climatiche.

La valutazione del progetto InnoWEE si baserà sui seguenti aspetti: l'efficienza energetica e la competitività dei pannelli (soprattutto in termini di costi di produzione e installazione), il rispetto del comfort interno agli edifici, la loro applicabilità anche a edifici storici e soprattutto al loro apporto in termini di sostenibilità ambientale e riduzione della CO₂ in atmosfera.

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